

"Linkages Between Wastewater Management and Public Health in Tirupattur District"

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Abstract

Tirupattur Urban District in Tamil Nadu faces significant challenges in domestic wastewater management, impacting public health and environmental sustainability. The district generates substantial volumes of wastewater daily, primarily from domestic sources, with a limited proportion undergoing treatment due to inadequate infrastructure. The existing system predominantly relies on septic tanks and open drains, leading to the direct discharge of untreated effluent into the environment. Challenges persist, including limited public awareness, inadequate maintenance of existing infrastructure and the need for stringent enforcement of sanitation regulations. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach, encompassing infrastructure development, public education and robust policy implementation to mitigate the health and environmental impacts of domestic wastewater in Tirupattur Urban District.

Keywords: *Domestic wastewater, health impact, infrastructure facilities*

Introduction

Domestic wastewater management is a critical concern for urban areas, particularly in fast-growing regions like Tirupattur District, Tamil Nadu. As urbanization accelerates, the volume of wastewater generated by households increases, posing significant challenges to both the economy and the environment. Inadequate treatment and disposal of domestic wastewater can lead to environmental degradation, health risks and additional economic burdens on communities. Understanding the implications of this issue is vital for developing effective policies and sustainable practices.

The economic impact of domestic wastewater is significant, particularly in urban areas where growing populations generate large volumes of waste. When wastewater is not properly treated, it leads to increased public health costs due to waterborne diseases,

contamination of drinking water sources, and environmental degradation. This not only puts financial pressure on healthcare systems but also affects the productivity of the workforce, as illnesses become more prevalent.

Domestic wastewater, generated from households, comprises a significant portion of global water pollution, posing challenges to sustainable water management. Worldwide, approximately the 359.4 billion cubic meters of wastewater are produced annually. While a significant portion, around 63%, is collected, only about 52% receives treatment. A considerable amount, around 48%, is discharged directly without any treatment, urban areas growing populations exacerbate the issue, with inadequate sanitation systems contributing to waterborne diseases and environmental degradation (United Nation, Water (UN-Water, 2022).

Domestic wastewater management presents significant environmental challenges, especially in urbanized regions. The state generates approximately 6,421 million liters per day (MLD) of sewage but the treatment capacity stands at around 2,348 MLD, leaving a significant gap of over 63% of wastewater untreated (CPCB, 2021).

Tirupattur District's urban municipalities Tirupattur, Jolarpettai, Vaniyambadi and Ambur collectively generated the 30 million liters per day (MLDs) of sewage. However, their combined sewage treatment capacity at only 18 MLDs, leaving a deficit at 12 MLDs, or 40%, were untreated sewage. Tirupattur municipality produces at 8 MLDs but has a treatment capacity of just at 3 MLD, resulting at 5 MLD of untreated sewage. Jolarpettai and Vaniyambadi were each generate at 6 MLD; Jolarpettai has an under-construction at 3 MLD plant, while Vaniyambadi at 4 MLD plant is also under construction. Ambur, the highest generator at 10 MLD, has an operational at 8 MLD plant but still lacks capacity for at 2 MLD. This infrastructure gap poses significant environmental and public health risks, underscoring the urgent need for investment in sewage treatment facilities to address the shortfall and ensure sustainable urban development.

Objectives

- To investigate the impact of domestic waste water on human health in the study area.
- To study the impact of domestic wastewater and its effect on ground water quality.

Methodology

The study descriptive and analytical design to assess the impact of poor domestic wastewater management in Tirupattur District, Tamil Nadu, utilizing a mixed-methods approach. Data were collected over three months using 530 stratified random samples, encompassing primary data from structured interviews, questionnaires, and focus group discussions, as well as secondary data from official reports and publications. Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical tools such as percentages, means, and regression analysis, while qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, providing a comprehensive understanding of wastewater generation and treatment practices in the municipalities

Review of Literature.

Manga. M et al. (2023) analyzed the public health performance of various sanitation technologies in Tamil Nadu, India, focusing on E. coli release as a measure of microbial contamination. Data, collected from 20 sanitation facilities, revealed significant variability in E. coli concentrations, with on-site systems like pit latrines and septic tanks showing higher contamination levels compared to centralized wastewater treatment plants. However, even centralized systems exceeded safe E. coli thresholds in 30% of cases. The importance of improved design, regular maintenance, monitoring and operator training was stressed to enhance sanitation performance and reduce waterborne disease risks, particularly in vulnerable communities.

Hasan, M et al. (2019), assessed water pollution in Bangladesh and its public health implications, focusing on contamination from industrial effluents, agricultural runoff and poor waste management. Data from 50 sites, including heavily polluted rivers like the Buriganga, revealed high levels of heavy metals, biological oxygen demand (BOD), and microbial contaminants. Arsenic contamination in groundwater was identified as a major

health risk, leading to chronic diseases. The study found clear link between water pollution and waterborne diseases, such as diarrhea and cholera. Stricter regulations, improved waste water management, and community education, are necessary to address these ongoing challenges and safeguard public health.

Tanimu and Adakole (2011) examined the environmental and public health impacts of discharging untreated domestic wastewater into natural water bodies in Northern Nigeria, focusing on communities near rivers and reservoirs. Analysis of 36 water samples, from 12 locations revealed significant contamination, with over 70% of samples exceeding WHO safety guidelines, particularly with high levels of nitrates, phosphates, heavy metals and fecal coliforms. Urban areas showed higher pollution due to dense populations and limited sewage infrastructure, as evident from frequent waterborne diseases like typhoid and cholera. With decentralized wastewater treatment, stricter regulations, and public awareness campaigns to these issues can be remedied.

Bindhy Wasini Pandey et al. (2017) domestic wastewater pollution creates many diseases, which spread easily during the rainy season due to bad quality of drainage as well as untreated effluent wastewater discharge into water source. Around 25 percent of all the human illnesses occur due to environment related pollution. Polluted water is the main cause for a number of diseases and their impact not only affects the present generation but also the future survival because its effect remains for a long period. Nearly 2.3 billion humans suffer from water borne diseases across the world. In many developing countries, many diseases like diarrhea, cholera, asthma, dysentery, typhoid, and enteric fever are due to poor quality of drinking water.

Mukesh Garg (2012) observed that domestic wastewater pollution is one of the biggest problems in India. Contaminated water produces serious effect from human health. Heavy metal and some other organic metals could cause cancer and other serious effects because is only 10 % of the waste water is treated and the remaining, without any treatment, is discharged into water sources.

Bagul et al. (2015) the sources of water contamination to be included biological, organic and inorganic wastes. The contamination of water is very hazardous for the human health and agricultural activities. It causes of water borne diseases such as diarrhea,

cholera; malaria, etc. which affect that human health. According to World Health Organization stated that, approximately 1.5 million human deaths occur, annually at the world level. The water borne diseases could be controlled through proper waste water treatment to protect human deaths.

Analysis and interpretation

Table: 1 Tirupattur District urban municipality STPs Details

S. I.	Municipalities	Total sewage generation (MLD)	Installed capacity (MLD)	Untreated (MLD)	Status
1	Tirupattur	8	3	5	Activated
2	Jolarpettai	6	3	3	Under construct
3	Vaniyambadi	6	4	2	Under construct
4	Ambur	10	8	2	Activated
	Total	30	18	12	

Sources: TNCPCB, report 2022-2023

The Table 1 sewage treatment infrastructure in Tirupattur District's urban municipalities reveals a concerning disparity between sewage generation and treatment capacity, with implications for both environmental sustainability and urban public health. The total sewage generated across the four municipalities Tirupattur, Jolarpettai, Vaniyambadi, and Ambur is 30 million liters per day (MLD), yet the cumulative installed capacity of sewage treatment plants (STPs) amounts to only 18 MLD. This leaves a significant shortfall of 12 MLD or 40% of the district's sewage currently untreated. Breaking down the data, Tirupattur municipality produces 8 MLD of sewage but has treatment capacity for only 3 MLD, resulting in 5 MLD of untreated sewage despite the STP being operational. The plant may be running at full capacity, yet unable to cope with current demand, creating potential overflow risks or illegal discharge into natural water bodies. In Jolarpettai and Vaniyambadi, which each generate 6 MLD of sewage, the situation is more precarious: both municipalities have STPs under construction, with capacities of 3 MLD and 4 MLD respectively, and currently discharge 3 MLD and 2 MLD of untreated sewage into the environment. The delayed completion of these facilities prolongs exposure to raw sewage and its associated health hazards. Ambur, the highest

sewage generator at 10 MLD, has the most robust infrastructure with an 8 MLD capacity plant that is currently operational, but still falls short by 2 MLD. Though relatively better equipped, Ambur still faces partial treatment limitations. The data revealed the a critical infrastructural large nearly half the sewage generated in this district goes untreated due to insufficient or incomplete facilities, but also to upgrade and expand capacity in Tirupattur and Ambur to meet both current and projected future demand in line with urban growth and sanitation goals.

Table:2 Ground water pH level in the Municipalities

Denomination	pH	Tirupattur		Jolarpettai		Vaniyambadi		Ambur	
		Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 1	Sample 2
Slightly alkaline	7.4 to 7.8	*	*	7.6	7.8	*	*	*	*
Moderately alkaline	7.9 to 8.4	7.9	8.0	*	*	8.0	8.1	8.1	8.2
Strongly alkaline	8.5 to 9.0	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Sources: Primary sample tested.

The Table 2 revealed the groundwater pH levels in Tirupattur, Jolarpettai, Vaniyambadi, and Ambur municipalities in Tamil Nadu predominantly fall within the moderately alkaline range of pH 7.9 to 8.4, aligning with the Bureau of Indian Standards' acceptable pH range for drinking water pH 6.5 to 8.5. The data for Jolarpettai and the lack of specific sample values for Tirupattur and Ambur limit comprehensive analysis. Moderately alkaline water is generally considered the safe for domestic use however, the consumption of water with higher alkalinity can lead to health issues, such as skin irritation and gastric discomfort. Therefore, regular monitoring and appropriate water treatment are essential to ensure the safety and quality of groundwater in these municipalities.

Table: 3. Domestic water usage per day and family size of the respondents

Water usage in Lt	Respondents family size				Total
	Up to 3	4 to 5	6 to 7	Above 8	
UP to 200 Lts	10	2	0	0	12
	(83.3%)	(16.7%)	(0.0%)	(0.0%)	(100.0%)
	[16.1%]	[0.7%]	[0.0%]	[0.0%]	[2.3%]
201 to 400 Lts	34	6	1	0	41
	(82.9%)	(14.6%)	(2.4%)	(0.0%)	(100.0%)
	[54.8%]	[2.2%]	[0.5%]	[0.0%]	[7.7%]
401 to 600 Lts	8	186	65	3	262
	(3.1%)	(71.0%)	(24.8%)	(1.1%)	(100.0%)
	[12.9%]	[67.4%]	[35.1%]	[42.9%]	[49.4%]
601 to 800 Lts	10	79	110	4	203
	(4.9%)	(38.9%)	(54.2%)	(2.0%)	(100.0%)
	[16.1%]	[28.6%]	[59.5%]	[57.1%]	[38.3%]
Above 801 Lts	0	3	9	0	12
	(0.0%)	(25.0%)	(75.0%)	(0.0%)	(100.0%)
	[0.0%]	[1.1%]	[4.9%]	[0.0%]	[2.3%]
Total	62	276	185	7	530
	(11.7%)	(52.1%)	(34.9%)	(1.3%)	(100.0%)
	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Note: Figures in () rows in percentages and those in [] are column percentages.

The Table: 5 provides an analysis of domestic water usage per day, based on household family size and their corresponding water consumption. The highest water usage category was 401 to 600 Lts and it was the most prominent across family sizes, particularly for households with 4 to 5 members represented by 186 respondents and 6 to 7 members represented 65 respondents, indicating that larger households generally consumed more water. Moving to the next category of 601 to 800 Lts, it was observed that 110 respondents with 6 to 7 members, came under this category, showing a trend of higher consumption in larger families. In contrast, the lowest water consumption was up to 200 Lts and it was most common for smaller families, particularly those with up to 3 members, represented by 10 respondents. The highest water usage of above 801 Lts, was reported within the family size of 6 to 7 group. The analysis revealed that as family size increased, so did the water consumption, with the 401-600 Lts category being the most significant water users by larger households.

Table: 4. Domestic water quality and cost of water collection

Water quality	Cost of water collection		Total
	Paid no tax	Paid Tax	
Highly Satisfied	8	50	58
	(13.8%)	(86.2%)	(100.0%)
	[6.4%]	[12.3%]	[10.9%]
Satisfied	20	46	66
	(30.3%)	(69.7%)	(100.0%)
	[16.0%]	[11.4%]	[12.5%]
Average	16	57	73
	(21.9%)	(78.1%)	(100.0%)
	[12.8%]	[14.1%]	[13.8%]
Dissatisfied	29	94	123
	(23.6%)	(76.4%)	(100.0%)
	[23.2%]	[23.2%]	[23.2%]
Highly Dissatisfied	52	158	210
	(24.8%)	(75.2%)	(100.0%)
	[41.6%]	[39.0%]	[39.6%]
Total	125	405	530
	(23.6%)	(76.4%)	(100.0%)
	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Note: Figures in () rows in percentages and those in [] are column percentages.

The Table: 4 explores the relationship between respondents' satisfaction with domestic water quality and their payment of water collection taxes. A significant portion of respondents, with 210 respondents, at 39.6 percent, were highly dissatisfied with the water quality 158 respondents paid their water taxes though they were highly dissatisfied with the quality of water. This group also represented the largest number of respondents who paid taxes despite their dissatisfaction with the water quality. In contrast, only 50 respondents, at 12.3 percent were highly satisfied and paid taxes, implying that those who were content with their water quality were less likely to feel burdened by water collection fees. The overall trend revealed that dissatisfaction with water quality was more prevalent among those who paid for water, but questioned the efficiency or value of the service provided in return for taxes.

Table: 5 Impact of poor water quality among the respondents family members

Affects public health	Family members affected by diseases					Total
	Typhoid Fever	Diarrhea	Cholera	Skin allergy	Viral fever	
Strongly Agree	38	6	40	40	13	137
	(27.7%)	(4.4%)	(29.2%)	(29.2%)	(9.5%)	(100.0%)
	[28.6%]	[20.7%]	[24.5%]	[30.8%]	[17.3%]	[25.8%]
Agree	55	12	74	39	38	218
	(25.2%)	(5.5%)	(33.9%)	(17.9%)	(17.4%)	(100.0%)
	[41.4%]	[41.4%]	[45.4%]	[30.0%]	[50.7%]	[41.1%]
Neutral	29	5	34	38	18	124
	(23.4%)	(4.0%)	(27.4%)	(30.6%)	(14.5%)	(100.0%)
	[21.8%]	[17.2%]	[20.9%]	[29.2%]	[24.0%]	[23.4%]
Disagree	5	1	14	4	3	27
	(18.5%)	(3.7%)	(51.9%)	(14.8%)	(11.1%)	(100.0%)
	[3.8%]	[3.4%]	[8.6%]	[3.1%]	[4.0%]	[5.1%]
Strongly Disagree	6	5	1	9	3	24
	(25.0%)	(20.8%)	(4.2%)	(37.5%)	(12.5%)	(100.0%)
	[4.5%]	[17.2%]	[0.6%]	[6.9%]	[4.0%]	[4.5%]
Total	133	29	163	130	75	530
	(25.1%)	(5.5%)	(30.8%)	(24.5%)	(14.2%)	(100.0%)
	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Note: Figures in () rows in percentages and those in [] are column percentages.

The Table: 5 reveals that the majority of respondents strongly agreed that poor water quality affected public health and family members' diseases. The highest number of 218 respondents, at 41.1 percent agreed that water quality was linked to diseases like typhoid fever, diarrhea, and cholera, 55 respondents at 41.4 percent agreed that typhoid fever was significantly influenced. Cholera also strongly linked to poor water quality, with 74 respondents, at 45.4 percent. It was followed closely by diarrhea by 12 respondents, at 41.4 percent and viral fever 38 respondents, at 50.7 percent. Neutral responses were also noteworthy, with 124 respondents, at 23.4 percent choosing to be neutral for its impact on public health. Disagreement levels were relatively low. Strong disagreement was rare across all diseases, with the highest being 9 respondents, at 37.5 percent to skin allergies. These patterns emphasize the strong perception that diseases like typhoid fever and cholera

were primarily influenced by poor water quality, with respondents less likely to link skin allergies or viral fever to water issues. In short, there was general consensus on the significant impact of contaminated water on health, particularly gastrointestinal diseases.

Table: 6. Monthly medical treatment cost by Municipalities

Treatment cost in Rs.	Name of the municipalities				Total
	Tirupattur	Jolarpettai	Vaniyambadi	Ambur	
Up to Rs. 300	26	12	30	27	95
	(27.4%)	(12.6%)	(31.6%)	(28.4%)	(100.0%)
	[18.6%]	[20.0%]	[16.7%]	[18.0%]	[17.9%]
Rs. 301 to 600	51	8	60	44	163
	(31.3%)	(4.9%)	(36.8%)	(27.0%)	(100.0%)
	[36.4%]	[13.3%]	[33.3%]	[29.3%]	[30.8%]
Rs. 601 to 900	42	7	54	28	131
	(32.1%)	(5.3%)	(41.2%)	(21.4%)	(100.0%)
	[30.0%]	[11.7%]	[30.0%]	[18.7%]	[24.7%]
Above Rs. 901	10	16	15	23	64
	(15.6%)	(25.0%)	(23.4%)	(35.9%)	(100.0%)
	[7.1%]	[26.7%]	[8.3%]	[15.3%]	[12.1%]
No cost	11	17	21	28	77
	(14.3%)	(22.1%)	(27.3%)	(36.4%)	(100.0%)
	[7.9%]	[28.3%]	[11.7%]	[18.7%]	[14.5%]
Total	140	60	180	150	530
	(26.4%)	(11.3%)	(34.0%)	(28.3%)	(100.0%)
	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Note: Figures in () rows in percentages and those in [] are column percentages.

The Table: 6, reveals the significant variation in medical treatment costs, across different municipalities. Treatment costs up to 300 was the highest proportion reported in Vaniyambadi, by 30 respondents, at 31.6 percent. It was closely followed by Ambur with 27 respondents, at 28.4 percent and Tirupattur with 26 respondents at 27.4 percent. Jolarpettai reported the smallest proportion in this category, with only 12 respondents at 12.6 percent. For treatment costs between 301 and 600, Tirupattur topped the list with 51 respondents at 36.4 percent, while Jolarpettai recorded the least at 8 respondents at 13.3 percent. Vaniyambadi and Ambur fall in between, with 60 respondents at 33.3 percent and 44 respondents at 29.3 percent, respectively. The 601 to 900 cost category revealed a similar trend, with Tirupattur having the highest percentage with 42 respondents at 32.1 percent,

while Jolarpettai recorded the lowest at 7 at 5.3 percent. Vaniyambadi and Ambur, with 54 respondents at 41.2 percent and 28 at 21.4 percent, respectively. For costs above 901, Ambur recorded the largest percentage with 23 respondents 35.9 percent, with Jolarpettai at 16 respondents at 25.0 percent, Vaniyambadi with 15 respondents at 23.4 percent, and Tirupattur at 10 respondents at 15.6 percent. The "No cost" category reported, the highest proportion in Jolarpettai with 17 respondents at 28.3 percent, followed by Ambur 18.7 percent, Vaniyambadi at 11.7 percent, and Tirupattur at 7.9 percent. The results revealed differences in medical treatment costs, with the highest costs found in Ambur and Jolarpettai, while Tirupattur and Vaniyambadi reported more varied cost distributions.

Table: 7. Man day loss

Man day loss	Name of the municipalities				Total
	Tirupattur	Jolarpettai	Vaniyambadi	Ambur	
Yes	85	36	109	88	318
	(26.7%)	(11.3%)	(34.3%)	(27.7%)	(100.0%)
	[60.7%]	[60.0%]	[60.6%]	[58.7%]	[60.0%]
No	55	24	71	62	212
	(25.9%)	(11.3%)	(33.5%)	(29.2%)	(100.0%)
	[39.3%]	[40.0%]	[39.4%]	[41.3%]	[40.0%]
Total	140	60	180	150	530
	(26.4%)	(11.3%)	(34.0%)	(28.3%)	(100.0%)
	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]	[100.0%]

Source: Computed from Primary Data

Note: Figures in () rows in percentages and those in [] are column percentages.

The Table: 7 illustrates distribution of man-day losses over the sample municipalities, 318 respondents, at 60 percent reported experiencing man-day loss due to health issues, with varying levels across municipalities. Vaniyambadi recorded the highest proportion of respondents with 109 respondents, at 60.6 percent, experiencing man-day loss, followed by Tirupattur at 85 respondents, at 60.7 percent and Ambur with 88 at 58.7 percent. Jolarpettai reported the lowest proportion, with 36 respondents, at 60 percent, reporting man-day loss. Ambur reported the highest proportion of 62 respondents who did not experience man-day loss at 41.3 percent. Tirupattur and Vaniyambadi followed with 55 respondents at 39.3 percent and with 71 at 39.4 percent, respectively. Jolarpettai reported man-day loss by 24 respondents at 40 percent. These trends revealed the broad

impact of health issues on workdays, across all areas, with Vaniyambadi and Tirupattur seeing the highest loss of man-days.

Table No. 8: One Way ANOVA test between impacts of poor domestic wastewater management

Factors		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Poor ground water quality directly affects public health	Between Groups	23.299	2	11.649	11.136	.000
	Within Groups	551.313	527	1.046		
	Total	574.611	529			
Effect of untreated domestic waste water effect on groundwater quality	Between Groups	21.225	2	10.613	10.386	.000
	Within Groups	538.527	527	1.022		
	Total	559.753	529			
Impact of groundwater contamination on local economy	Between Groups	67.197	2	33.599	23.859	.000
	Within Groups	742.131	527	1.408		
	Total	809.328	529			
Effects on income, livestock	Between Groups	28.313	2	14.157	181.964	.000
	Within Groups	41.000	527	.078		
	Total	69.313	529			

Source: Computed from Primary Data

The Table: 8, presents the results of One-Way ANOVA, to analyze the impact of poor domestic wastewater management, across different factors. For each factor, the analysis included Between Groups and Within Groups variations, along with statistical values. The first factor, Poor groundwater quality directly affects public health, revealed significant differences between groups with an F-value of 11.136 and a p-value of .000, indicating strong evidence that groundwater quality did affect the public health. Similarly, the second factor, untreated domestic wastewater effect on groundwater quality, also revealed significant results, with an F-value of 10.386 and a p-value of .000, suggesting untreated wastewater did impact the groundwater quality. The third factor, Groundwater contamination's impact on the local economy, reported a higher F-value of 23.859, again

with a p-value of .000, confirming significant economic effects due to groundwater contamination. The fourth factor, effects on income and livestock, reported an extraordinarily high F-value of 181.964, indicating a very strong and statistically significant relationship between wastewater management and economic impact on income and livestock. For all factors, the p-values were less than the threshold of 0.05, signifying that poor wastewater management significantly affected public health, groundwater quality, local economy and livestock.

Conclusion

A recent survey across several municipalities highlights significant concerns regarding water usage, quality, and wastewater management. Over half of the respondents (53%) reported using up to 100 liters of water daily for toilet purposes, with households of 4 to 5 members constituting the majority (58.4%) of this group. Despite paying water taxes, 39.6% expressed high dissatisfaction with water quality. The most common water usage category was 401 to 600 liters per day, particularly among larger households. Health concerns were prevalent, with 41.1% linking poor water quality to diseases like typhoid, diarrhea and cholera. Additionally, 60% reported man-day losses due to health issues, indicating a broad impact on productivity. A majority agreed that improving wastewater management would enhance public health, with Vaniyambadi and Ambur showing the strongest support. Notably, 84.5% of respondents acknowledged being affected by sewage water pollution. The preferred solutions included upgrading wastewater treatment facilities and launching public awareness campaigns. Statistical analysis (One-Way ANOVA) confirmed significant impacts of poor wastewater management on public health, groundwater quality, local economy and livestock, with all p-values below 0.05, underscoring the urgency for comprehensive water and wastewater management reforms.

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